

A Brief Note on Disease Screening in Exotic Pet Birds

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Abstract

Exotic pet trade is increasing on daily basis throughout the world and this trade mostly includes mammals, reptiles, and avian individuals. Some of the exotic insects are also being traded. The entire trade is dependent on legal status of a particular species and legal permissions. Out of all, exotic birds are generally preferred by enthusiasts, passionate owners and local people who keep them as indoor pets for various reasons. These birds may encounter various health issues which are required to be addressed in due course of time in developing countries. The present documentation highlights some of the important factors while screening diseases of exotic pet birds.

Introduction

Identification of diseases and disorders of a bird which has entered in a newer territory (either by flying naturally or after being traded as an exotic pet) is of a great challenge to veterinarians. It is crucial to understand basic anatomy and physiology of such birds before identifying any disease, understanding of pathogenesis, evaluating mode of transmission as well as establishing diagnosis, treatment, prevention and control strategies. Most of the avian disease investigations in countries like India are based on those which have been reported in poultry birds considering their economic significance in the country. In past, various veterinarians and scientists have made attempts to document some of the disease conditions in exotic pet birds. It is also possible that exotic pet birds may show similar disease which are commonly seen in poultry birds. However, exotic pet birds may encounter variable types of diseases and can also act as a source of infection to other native birds or humans (e.g., in case of zoonotic diseases). All exotic birds which are traded from different countries end-up mostly in a newer environment where they can face abrupt and sudden changes in environment, management, handling, feeding, housing, veterinary care etc. Hence, it is important to address the need to evaluate disease screening in exotic pet birds.

What is needed?

Exotic birds like Budgerigars, Cockatiels, Zebra Finches, Conures, Macaws, African Grey Parrots, Lovebirds etc. are available widely in the exotic pet bird market (local and global market) throughout the world. These birds mostly spend their lives in captivity till death. Some of the exotic birds are kept as display birds or as part of *ex-situ* conservation in zoos while many exotic birds are kept as indoor pets or companions. Hence, their health significantly depends on managerial practices adopted by handlers and strategic planning is needed to understand and identify their diseases. Following important step-wise points are required to be considered while screening diseases in exotic pet birds.

- Knowledge on species/type of bird and its natural habitat/origin. One should always consider permissions necessary for trade of such birds in different regions and their conservation status. There are various societies and international bodies which are monitoring trade of birds throughout the world. Some of the examples for checking conservation status and trade related aspects include visiting official portals of IUCN, CITES, TRAFFIC international etc. Nation-wise rules and regulations should also be considered while getting information on exotic bird being examined as some of the native species are not allowed for purchase or sale (e.g., Indian Peacock is protected under the Indian Wildlife Protection Act and is not allowed to be kept as an indoor pet in India).
- Understanding and reviewing its anatomy, behaviour, physiology and biochemistry by using available resources.
- Understanding management practices: Feeding, housing, grooming, wing-clipping, training/taming, size of cage, feeding frequencies, provision of water, seasonal challenges, handling, cage-enrichment etc. at place of stay/captivity.
- Careful collection of history pertaining to healthy and diseased birds: Aspects on source/origin, place of procurement, transportation details, stress conditions, behaviour, previous management practices etc.
- Examination of birds from distance.
- Careful physical restraint: Owners' or handlers' or caretakers' consent must be taken prior to conducting physical handling and examination in all cases. Efforts should be made to reduce drastic fluctuations in body temperature, heart rate, respiration rate, breathing etc. while handling. Gentle restraint is very crucial.
- Detailed physical examination: Facial expression, head region, neck, dorsal abdomen, chest region/keel bone, wings, legs and vent area.
- Collection of biomaterials: Feather samples (by gentle plucking), ectoparasites (using tweezers or water-soaked paper), impression smears, blood (e.g., from wing vein using suitable sized sterile

needles), excreta/droppings (e.g., either fresh samples from floor of the cage or directly from vent/cloaca using swabs of size suitable for bird being examined), lesions (if any). Out of all, faecal samples are very useful for diagnostic purposes as they can be used to observe dietary material and to detect presence of internal parasites as well as microorganisms.

- Imaging techniques: Such as radiographs (e.g., for fractures, crop engorgement, crop fistula, air sac rupture, gastric obstruction, foreign body ingestion etc.), ultrasound examination (e.g., for cardiac and gastrointestinal diseases), magnetic resonance imaging/MRI or computed tomography/CT scan (e.g., to identify space-occupying lesions in brain, muscle etc.).
- Microbiology: Use of bacterial cultural examination, fungal isolation, virus isolation, animal inoculation tests, fecal sample examination, blood smear examination, stereoscopic examination of ectoparasites for identification etc. to identify etiologies microscopically.
- Pathological investigations: Hematobiochemistry, histopathological examinations using tissues, post-mortem observations in mass-mortalities etc. are important to investigate underlying pathologic changes in many diseases.
- Special tests like ELISA, PCR, RIA, biotechnology techniques etc. for confirmatory diagnosis.
- Correlating the findings with existing literature on similar diseases observed in birds in past.
- Checking suitability of different therapeutic drugs depending on reviewed literature, experience and availability in different regions.
- Dissemination of findings with concerned persons, veterinarians, scientific community etc. is also of great importance after disease screening.

Conclusion

It is important to screen exotic pet birds for existing clinical health ailments (infectious and non-infectious conditions), internal and external parasites, microbiota present in their excreta and their health impact in order to establish disease prevention and control strategies in future. Careful collection of history, step-wise physical examination, careful handling/restraint, appropriate diagnostic methodologies and treatment options are of great importance to generate basic database for avian veterinary practitioners in developing countries.

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